

Distinct Onychoscopic Patterns in Clinical Variants of Onychomycosis: Insights from a South Indian Tertiary Care CentreHeera Ab^{1*}, Chandran R², George Ae³^{1,2,3}Dept. of Dermatology and Venereology, Govt. Medical College, Thiruvananthapuram

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Abstract:

Background: Onychomycosis is an infection of the nail unit caused by fungi. Onychoscopy is a quick, non-invasive, office-based diagnostic tool for the examination of nail unit and its components by magnification, using a dermoscope enabling observation of nail features that are not visible to the naked eye. Certain dermoscopic patterns demonstrate 100% specificity for onychomycosis. This study aims to contribute towards the development of onychoscopy based diagnostic criteria for onychomycosis in the near future.

Objective: To identify the onychoscopic patterns in confirmed cases of onychomycosis and the association between the onychoscopic patterns and the clinical variants of onychomycosis.

Materials and Methods: 80 cases of clinically diagnosed onychomycosis who tested positive for fungus by either microscopy or culture were subjected to onychoscopic examination with a 150x magnification dermoscope.

Results: The most common onychoscopic pattern associated with onychomycosis was distal irregular termination (37.5%). DLSO nails were significantly associated with longitudinal striae (38.3%), distal irregular termination (34.7%) and jagged proximal edge (28%). TDO nails were significantly associated with ruin pattern (68.6%) and lamellar microsplitting (60%). Cloud pattern (83.3%) was found to be significantly associated with PSO. WSO had a significant association with grid pattern (100%). The newly reported blue globules was also observed in this study.

Conclusion: The most common onychoscopic pattern associated with onychomycosis was distal irregular termination. This study was also able to establish significant relationship between individual clinical variants of onychomycosis and some of the onychoscopic patterns.

Keywords: Onychomycosis, Onychoscopy, Dermoscopy, Potassium hydroxide, Distal irregular termination

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Introduction

Onychomycosis is a fungal infection of the nail caused by dermatophytes, non-dermatophytes and yeasts. [1] The physical appearance of dystrophic nails cause psychological distress and the local pain can impede daily activity. [2] The prevalence of onychomycosis is rising due to increased risk factors and rate of case detection. [3]

Onychomycosis is readily curable with antifungal agents. [4] However, the expense of medications and the prolonged course of treatment can hinder treatment adherence. [5] An early and correct diagnosis will ensure proper usage of oral antifungals. [6]

The slow progression of onychomycosis, gives clinicians adequate time to perform thorough investigations without compromising patient outcomes. The ideal diagnostic techniques need to work for both the clinician and the patient, in terms of timeline, cost and reporting outcome. [7]

The multitude of diagnostic techniques available include conventional microscopy, fungal culture and

histopathological examination as well as newer modalities like onychoscopy, reflectance confocal microscopy, molecular assays and artificial intelligence. [8]

Onychoscopy is a quick, non-invasive, office-based diagnostic tool that involves examination of nail unit and its components by magnification using a dermoscope that enables easier and closer observation of nail features that are otherwise not visible to the naked eye. [9] Its advantages are prompt and non-invasive assessment of the entire nail unit compared to mycological examinations which is invasive and time consuming. Certain dermoscopic patterns demonstrate 100% specificity for onychomycosis, like jagged proximal edges, spiked pattern and aurora borealis. Thus nail dermoscopy is an effective tool for diagnosis when mycological diagnosis is unavailable. [10] But studies that describe dermoscopic features of onychomycosis are few and those exploring dermoscopic patterns specific to subtypes of onychomycosis are even fewer. [11] Hence this

study.

Material and Methods

Study Type: Hospital based cross-sectional study conducted in the Department of Dermatology at a tertiary care centre in South India and approved by the institutional ethics committee.

Study Participants: A total of 123 consenting patients with a clinical diagnosis of onychomycosis were included. Patients who had negative results for fungal microscopy, culture and histopathology and who had received antifungal treatment in last 3 months were excluded from the study.

History and Clinical Examination: Detailed history was taken and general physical examination and a thorough dermatological examination was done. The morphological types of onychomycosis was noted. Relevant investigations were done.

Onychoscopy: A total of 248 suspect nails were subjected to onychoscopic examination using a Video dermatoscope (2 in 1 hair and skin analyser, DermaIndia, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India) with 50x magnification. Isopropyl alcohol/ Liquid paraffin was used as an interface medium where needed. Polarising and non-polarizing views were made use of. The following Onychoscopic patterns were recognized: [11-16]

1. Onycholysis
2. Longitudinal striae
3. Spiked pattern- indentations at the proximal edge of nail with onycholysis
4. Jagged proximal edge- the proximal margin of the onycholytic area is characterized by a jagged edge
5. Distal irregular termination - distal pulverization of the nail plate
6. Ruin appearance - indentation on the ventral portion of the nail plate due to accumulation of dermal debris
7. Aurora Borealis- Parallel band of varying colors
8. Grid pattern - White linear striae forming a grid pattern
9. Cloud pattern - white patches of true leukonychia visible through a transparent nail plate
10. Lamellar micro-splitting
11. Transverse white lines

Direct Microscopy and Culture

Nail clippings and scrapings were collected from the affected part of the nail including the subungual debris using a sterile blunt scalpel blade. This material was placed on a glass slide and 2-3 drops of 40% Potassium hydroxide (KOH) and one drop of Chicago Sky Blue stain was added. The slides were then subjected to gentle heat fixation and incubated for 2- 48 hrs. Microscopic examination was done by a single untrained observer under scanner mode

(4x), low power (10x), high power (40x) and oil immersion (100x) objectives of an ordinary light microscope, for long branched filamentous hyphae with or without arthrospores (dermatophytes), pseudohyphae (candida), mycelia, arthrospores or yeast cells (non-dermatophytic molds) that are stained blue against a pink background. This examination was done first at two hours. If negative, it was repeated at 24 hours and further at 48 hours.

If there was a strong clinical suspicion of onychomycosis but KOH examination was negative *thrice*, then culture and histopathological examination with PAS staining of nail clipping was attempted to prove primary onychomycosis

For culture, nail clipping was sent in a sterile filter paper for inoculation on Sabouraud's dextrose agar medium with and without cycloheximide (0.5g/l), at 25°C for optimal growth. In the case of growth, colony characteristics were studied on lactophenol cotton blue wet mount preparation. Absence of growth after 4 weeks of incubation was considered negative for fungus.

Data Analysis: Data was coded and tabulated for analysis. Categorical and quantitative variables were expressed as frequency and mean \pm standard deviation respectively. Chi-square test was used to find association between the clinical variants of onychomycosis and onychoscopic patterns. For all statistical interpretations, $p < 0.05$ was considered the threshold for statistical significance. Statistical analysis was performed by using a statistical software package SPSS, version 20.0.

Results

One hundred and twenty three clinically diagnosed cases of onychomycosis were subjected to onychoscopy and microscopic examination with KOH and Chicago Sky Blue stain. Of the 82 that showed onychoscopic features suggestive of onychomycosis, only 78 tested positive for fungus by microscopy and 2 by fungal culture. These 80 patients were included in the study, among whom 248 nails were involved.

In this study, we noticed that 43(53.8%) of the 80 individuals had involvement of toe nails only, 21(26.3%) had involvement of finger nail only and 16(20%) had both finger nail and toe nail infection concomitantly. The most commonly involved nail out of the 248 nails studied was the right big toe (52, 21%).

The most common variant of onychomycosis was distal lateral subungual onychomycosis (DLSO) (193, 77.8%) followed by total dystrophic onychomycosis (TDO) (35, 14.1%), proximal subungual onychomycosis (PSO) (18, 7.3%) and white superficial onychomycosis (WSO) (2, 0.8%).

Onycholysis was present in 116 (46.8%).

Of the 248 nails, 216 (87.09%) had white discolouration. The others were yellow (86, 34.6%), brown (48, 19.3%), black (39, 15.72%), grey (31, 12.5%), green (12, 4.8%), blue (1, 0.4%).

Onychoscopy

The most common onychoscopic pattern observed was distal irregular termination (93, 37.5%) followed by longitudinal striae (81, 32.7%). Others were spiked pattern (58, 23.4%), jagged proximal

edge (54, 21.8%), aurora borealis pattern (43, 17.3%), ruin appearance (33, 13.3%), lamellar microsplitting (30, 12.1%), transverse white lines (29, 11.7%), cloud pattern (15, 6%), grid pattern (2, 0.8%) and blue globule (1, 0.4%) (Figure 1). The blue globule is not a previously recognised onychoscopic pattern pertaining to onychomycosis. The onychoscopic patterns observed in specific clinical type of onychomycosis is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Correlation between onychoscopic patterns and clinical variant of onychomycosis

Pattern	% in DLSO	% in TDO	% in PSO	% in WSO	p
Distal Irregular Termination	34.7	74.3	0	0	<0.01
Longitudinal striae	38.3	17.1	5.6	0	0.003
Jagged proximal edge	28	0	0	0	<0.01
Ruin appearance	4.7	68.6	0	0	<0.01
Lamellar microsplitting	4.1	60	5.6	0	<0.01
Grid pattern	0	0	0	100	<0.01
Cloud pattern	0	0	83.3	0	<0.01
Spiked pattern	26.9	8.6	16.7	0	0.082
Aurora borealis	20.0	8.6	5.6	0	0.161
Transverse white lines	13.5	2.9	11.1	0	0.320
Blue globules	0.5	0	0	0	0.963

Figure 1: Blue globules

Discussion

The most common variant of onychomycosis seen was DLSO (77.8%) followed by TDO (14.1%), PSO and WSO. There were no nails with endonyx onychomycosis. The study by Kayarkatte et al, Devi Sangeetha et al and Chetana et al had an almost similar study sample. [12, 16, 17]

Out of the 248 nails, 87.09% had white discolouration, followed by yellow (34.6%), brown (19.3%), black, grey, green and blue. The predominant colour change noted by Devi Sangeetha et al, was yellow (66.3%) [12] and by

Chetana et al, was brown (75.2%). [17] The updated review on onychomycosis by Leung et al, showed that yellow brown discolouration was considered the typical manifestation of onychomycosis. [3]

Onycholysis was seen in only 46.8% of nails in our study, while Kayarkatte et al, reported 96.6% onycholysis. [16]

The most common onychoscopic pattern noticed in this study was distal irregular termination (37.5%) (Figure 2) followed by longitudinal striae (32.7%) and spiked pattern (23.4%) (Figure 3). Other patterns observed included jagged proximal edge

(21.8%), aurora borealis pattern (17.3%) (Figure 4), transverse white lines (11.7%), ruin pattern (13.3%), lamellar microsplitting (12.1%), cloud pattern (6%), rid pattern (0.8%) and blue globules (0.4%). In other studies, the predominant pattern was spiked pattern (80.3% [12] and 86.4% [16]), while in others, it was longitudinal striae (60.65%), distal irregular

termination (43.22%) and spiked pattern (25.16%). [14] In addition to longitudinal striae (49.1%), spiked pattern (43.16%) and distal irregular termination (34.6%), Chetana et al observed a novel pattern that they termed as blue globules in 8.9% of nails. [17] In our study we were able to observe this pattern in one DLSO nail.

Figure 2: Distal irregular termination

Figure 3: Spiked pattern

Figure 4: Aurora borealis pattern

In our study, longitudinal striae was found to be the most prevalent onychoscopic pattern in DLSO nails (38.3%, $p=0.003$) followed by distal irregular termination (34.7%, $p<0.01$) and jagged proximal edge (28%, $p<0.01$) (Figure 5), all achieving statistical significance. Spiked pattern was found in 26.9% of DLSO nails and achieved only near significance ($p=0.08$). In contrast, spiked pattern was found to be significantly associated with DLSO

with a prevalence of 90.3% in the study by Kayarkatte et al. [16] Chetana et al found the spiked pattern (52%) and jagged pattern (29.9%) to be the predominant patterns in DLSO that were statistically significant. [17] Spiked pattern (90.5%), distal irregular termination (8%) and longitudinal striae (91%) were found to be statistically significant patterns in the 2021 study by Devi Sangeetha et al. [12]

Figure 5: Jagged proximal edge

In our study, 74.3% of TDO nails had distal irregular termination, 68.6% had ruin pattern (Figure 6) and 60% had lamellar microsplitting. All of these associations were statistically significant ($p<0.01$). Kayarkatte et al, in their study found a significant association between TDO and ruin appearance and longitudinal striae. Although they could not

establish statistical significance, lamellar microsplitting was found to be associated with 81.8% of TDO cases. [16] In the study by Devi Sangeetha et al, a statistically significant association was drawn between TDO and ruin appearance (100%) as well as distal irregular termination (100%). [12]

Figure 6: Ruin pattern

Our study had 83.3% of PSO nails significantly associated with cloud pattern ($p < 0.01$) (Figure 7). A similar cloud pattern was observed in 100% cases of PSO in other reports,^{12, 16} but a significance could not be drawn between cloud pattern and PSO in both.

Figure 7: Cloud Pattern

In 2020 Grover et al, reported the appearance of a novel onychoscopic finding of grid pattern (Figure 8) associated with WSO.¹⁵ In our study, we were able to observe this pattern in both cases of WSO (100%) with a good margin of significance ($p < 0.01$).

Figure 8: Grid Pattern

Simultaneous existence of 2 onychoscopic patterns was noted in 95 (38.3%) nails. A maximum of 5 onychoscopic patterns in a single nail were observed in 5 (2%) nails. In a 2018 study, 25.9% of patients had 2 coexisting dermoscopic findings in a single nail. [10]

This study has evaluated the onychoscopic patterns of all the 248 involved nails of each subject enrolled in the study. This differs from other similar studies where they have selected only one representative nail from a single study subject and then evaluated the onychoscopic patterns of that nail in detail. This has helped us with the dilemma of having to choose a representative nail in those individuals where a combination of variants of onychomycosis exists in the same individual. We believe this has also helped to include an assortment of onychoscopic patterns into our data set which might otherwise have been missed.

Limitation

- Small sample size

Conclusion

Onychomycosis is a fungal infection of the nail unit that is prevalent all over the world. An accurate diagnosis of onychomycosis should precede an effective treatment as in any other disease. The sensitivity of conventional methods for fungal detection are significantly lower for the nail. This is where onychoscopy comes into play. In this study, we have evaluated the dermoscopic features of onychomycosis in detail. In addition to having been able to detect the most commonly associated dermoscopic patterns in the different types of onychomycosis, we were also able to observe some of the new onychoscopic patterns, like grid pattern

and blue globules amongst our patients. We have also succeeded in establishing significant relationship between individual clinical variants of onychomycosis and some of the onychoscopic patterns. Although onychoscopy is still a developing area of diagnostics, many of our findings are consistent with that of previous studies from around the globe. The onychoscope, as of now, is an effective adjunctive tool in the diagnosis of onychomycosis along with microscopy and culture to increase the diagnostic accuracy. In the future, onychoscopy might form the crux of diagnostic criterias of onychomycosis.

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